

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish & Wildlife Office
650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300
Sacramento, California 95814-4700

In reply refer to:
2022-0044363-S7-001

December 12, 2024

Lindsay Vivian
Office Chief
Office of Biological Sciences and Permits
California Department of Transportation, District 4
P.O. Box 23660, MS-8B
Oakland, California 94623

Subject: Formal Consultation on the State Route 37 Petaluma River Bridge Project, Marin County, California (*MRN-37-PM 14.50, EA 04-2Q500/ID 0419000019*)

Dear Lindsay Vivian:

This letter is in response to the California Department of Transportation's (Caltrans) December 15, 2023, letter requesting formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) on the effects of the proposed State Route (SR) 37 Petaluma River Bridge Project (project) located in Marin County, California. Caltrans has determined that the proposed project may affect but is not likely to adversely affect the federally endangered California red-legged frog (*Rana draytonii*) (CRLF), and has determined the project may affect and is likely to adversely affect the endangered California Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus obsoletus*) (CRR) and the endangered San Francisco Bay-Delta distinct population segment of the longfin smelt (*Spirinchus thaleichthys*) (LFS). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

In reviewing this project, the Service has relied upon: (1) Caltrans' December 15, 2023, letter requesting formal, informal, and conference consultation; (2) the December 2023 *Petaluma River Bridge Project Biological Assessment* (BA) prepared by Caltrans; (3) electronic mail, telephone, and other communications between the Service and Caltrans from December 2023 to November 2024; and (4) other information available to the Service.

California Red-legged Frog

Suitable habitat for the CRLF occurs within a small portion of the Action Area. The land directly northeast of the Petaluma River Bridge is made up of historical baylands converted to grasslands

and hayfields, including irrigation ditches and drainages. The irrigation ditches and drainages provide potential freshwater breeding habitat that could serve as sources for frogs dispersing into or adjacent to the Action Area. These features also provide conduits for dispersal between more remote breeding habitat and the Action Area. The closest record of CRLF occurs less than 2 miles northeast of the eastern terminus of the Action Area, within a small drainage pool. The land cover mapped between the drainage pool and the Action Area is predominantly an undeveloped hayfield, annual and perennial grassland, and freshwater marsh. The Action Area is within the maximum dispersal distance of the drainage pool and the grassland and hayfield within the Action Area could provide upland dispersal habitat because these areas are devoid of barriers to dispersal. However, the grassland habitat within the project limits includes highly disturbed herbaceous roadside vegetation that is annually mowed and maintained. It is unlikely that the species would use this area for upland refugia when there is mesic hayfield habitat nearby that is located further from the roadway. Grassland habitat mapped within the Action Area to the west of the Petaluma River is not considered suitable habitat because it includes barriers to dispersal in the form of SR 37 and surrounding development. The Petaluma River at this location is not considered suitable aquatic habitat due to high salinity, and there are no other suitable aquatic habitat locations within the Action Area. The area of concern for the CRLF occurs along an approximate 2-acre strip on the eastern side of the bridge alongside the highway that will be used for temporary staging. This is relatively small in scope and size and its proximity to the highway likely deters CRLF from dispersing into the Action Area. Despite having both suitable aquatic and upland habitats available for the CRLF to utilize, no CRLF have been documented within a mile of the Action Area. Based on the lack of any recent detections and the habitat factors described above, it is unlikely that CRLF would occur within the Action Area; however, the probability is not zero because nearby suitable habitat is still present.

In the unlikely event that a CRLF is detected during implementation of the bridge rehabilitation actions, Caltrans is proposing several conservation measures such as installing wildlife exclusion fencing, the employment of a Service-approved biological monitor, worker awareness training, and preconstruction surveys. Caltrans is also proposing avoidance measures such as work stoppage and the observation of the Service's recommended work window for CRLF (April 15 to October 31) in areas not previously enclosed with wildlife exclusion fencing.

The Service concurs with Caltrans' determination that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the CRLF based on the lack of occurrences, minimal suitable wetland habitat within the Action Area, and the implementation of conservation and avoidance measures.

The remainder of this document represents the Service's biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the CRR and LFS.

CONSULTATION HISTORY

December 18, 2023	The Service received Caltrans' December 15, 2023, request for initiation of consultation for the project.
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- March 7, 2024 The Service held a telephone conversation with Caltrans about construction noise and disturbances with regard to the CRR and recommended conservation measures. The Service also requested that surveys proposed by Caltrans for CRR be withdrawn from the project description and that Caltrans could assume presence of CRR based on current occurrence data.
- March 20, 2024 Caltrans responded to the previous telephone conversation via electronic mail proposing conservation measures and rationale for certain construction related effects that could be considered not likely to adversely affect the CRR based on location and distance from areas where CRR could occur.
- August 26, 2024 The Service held a video conference meeting with Caltrans to discuss conservation measures with regard to pile driving effects and noise reduction measures for CRR. Caltrans agreed to utilize some form of cushioning block for pile driving to reduce noise effects.
- August 27, 2024 Caltrans notified the Service via email that vibratory methods or a cushioning block couldn't be utilized due to the engineering of the pile driving.
- September 2024-
October 2024 Caltrans and the Service exchanged email communication to discuss potential alternative noise reduction measures.
- October 23, 2024 Caltrans sent the Service an email which stated that installation of these piles with a vibratory head driver does not meet the required pile capacity versus installation by direct push and impact hammering. This is due to the differences in skin friction along the pile and that vibratory pile installation is not recommended for this project due to the need to have sufficient impact to drive the pile deep enough into the substrate in order for the pile to withstand lateral forces in the event of a vessel collision.
- October 30, 2024 The Service responded to Caltrans' email requesting noise monitoring for impact pile driving to minimize the potential for exceeding peak noise thresholds.
- November 21, 2024 Caltrans responded to the Service's request and provided an additional conservation measure that provided noise monitoring for pile driving.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

Caltrans proposes to rehabilitate the Petaluma River Bridge deck, upgrade the bridge railings, and replace the bridge fender system to meet current safety standards to maintain the structure in a reliable and serviceable condition.

Bridge Deck Rehabilitation

Bridge rehabilitation activities would involve replacing the asphalt concrete (AC) deck and approach slabs. The existing 2 to 4 inches of AC deck pavement would be removed and an evaluation of the deck condition and needed repairs would be made. The roadway surface would then be replaced with 2 inches of polyester concrete and restriped. The new polyester concrete deck surfacing would match the profile of the existing AC deck pavement elevation. All signs and object markers located along the bridge and its approaches would be relocated or reset in place. No new lighting is proposed. The approach slabs supporting the roadways surface at the east and west ends of the bridge would be replaced. The existing slabs would be removed, and a form built to construct new approach slabs would be assembled. The new approach slabs would be cast in place. The existing finger joints and header dams would be replaced with Caltrans standard strip joint seal assemblies. The existing pourable joint seals, typically used at each bent support, would be replaced in kind with Type A joint seals. A portion of the existing median barrier would need to be removed to facilitate the replacement of the finger joints. These portions of the median barrier would be removed and replaced in-kind.

Bridge Railing Replacement and Upgrade

The project would replace and upgrade the existing 4,412 feet of concrete baluster bridge railing with a Type 85 concrete barrier along both sides of the bridge. The bridge will be widened 1 foot on each side from the addition of each new railing. In addition to the bridge railing replacement, the metal beam guardrail approaches and departures would be replaced with Midwest guardrail system (MGS) as necessary, with transition railing between the guardrail and the proposed bridge railing. To provide a standard connection between the MGS and the proposed bridge railing, 25 feet of the existing guardrail would be removed and replaced with the standard transition railing WB-31. Drainage facilities will also be constructed to convey stormwater off the bridge and into the adjacent area. A long above-ground drainage pipe to the west of the Petaluma River Bridge will be replaced and improvements will be made to drainage on the east end of the bridge.

Bridge Fender System Replacement

The existing timber bridge fender system would be removed and replaced. The proposed fender system would be comprised of approximately 96 piles. The new fender system would consist of 24-inch steel pipe piles and steel walers with plastic lumber sheathing. The vertical limit of the fender system would be increased to allow for the anticipated sea level rise. Navigation lighting would be upgraded to meet the current U.S. Coast Guard requirements. Based on available

subsurface information at the site, the topsoil layer at Bents 7 and 8 is soft clay. The approximate thickness of this clay layer at Bent 7 is 15 feet, and that at Bent 8 is 27 feet. This soft clay layer is anticipated to show very low soil resistance; therefore, the proposed piles shall be directly pushed through this layer with no or negligible impact hammering on the piles. Below this soft clay layer, the piles will need to be driven by impact hammering to get the necessary pile capacity. Initial pile driving involves intensive monitoring and takes approximately 2-4 days to install the initial 2-3 piles. The methods should allow 7-10 piles installed per day, resulting in 10-18 working days total where impact hammer pile driving may occur.

Construction Staging and Traffic Management

One staging area would be utilized for construction east of the bridge and adjacent to the westbound lanes would be used for construction access, staging, and laydown. The unpaved areas used for staging will be revegetated with native plant seed species similar to adjacent habitat. The Black Point Boat Launch would be used for loading and unloading of barges for work within the Petaluma River.

Construction traffic management would primarily involve one or full lane closures in each direction during non-peak hours in order to perform deck rehabilitation, replace approach slabs, construct the bridge railing, and install MGS. Work on the eastern side of the bridge would be within the right of way (ROW).

Work on the fender systems in the Petaluma River, will require temporary access via the Black Point Boat Launch area, at the west end of the bridge, to bring in equipment and materials. In-water work below the bridge would be conducted during daytime hours only. Work in the navigational channel would be conducted using barges to replace the fender system at bents 7 and 8.

Construction of the fender system may require multiple barges to do the work, if one barge is for a crane and other construction equipment, while one or more barges will be used to hold supplies or transport materials from the boat ramp to the working barge. The work area around the existing and new fender system would first be enclosed in materials to minimize construction disturbance, including (at minimum) a sediment boom to contain suspended sediment and bubble curtain to reduce hydroacoustic pressure pulses. The existing wood fender system would be removed by vibrating piles. If complete pile removal is not possible with vibratory methods, wood piles will be cut and removed to 3 feet below the mudline. The new, steel fender support piles would first be vibrated in, then driven to tip with an impact hammer, then the remaining fender elements would be installed.

The proposed fender system would be comprised of 96 piles. Pile driving activities could last up to 32 days depending on installation rate. The piles might be installed in segments (i.e., not consecutively) due to limited clearance of the bridge. Replacement of the fender system is anticipated to be completed in two months within one construction season.

Right of Way

All work on the bridge or substructure, including the proposed widening due to the new bridge rail, would occur within the existing State ROW. The access area at the Black Point Boat Launch will require a temporary construction easement of approximately 33,540-square-foot (0.77 acre).

Construction Equipment

Equipment used for project activities would include, but not be limited to, the following: rollers and grinders; a backhoe and/or bobcat; concrete trucks and long-reach concrete pump trucks; temporary barges; pile driver; lifts, generators, hoe ram, jackhammers/breakers, dump trucks, and saw-cut machines. Table 1 lists the equipment anticipated to be used with the maximum noise emission levels expected from standard equipment.

Table 1. Standard Construction Equipment Noise Emission Levels

Equipment	Actual Measured L_{MAX} at 50 feet from Source (dBA) Noise Level
Pile driver (IMPACT)	95
Vibratory pile driver	95
Pavement saw	90 (concrete saw)
Pavement grinder (cold planer)	90 (pavement scarifier)
Crane	85
Concrete mixer	85
Jackhammer	85
Dozer	85
Flatbed truck	84
Concrete pump truck	82
Generator	82
Compressor	80
Rollers	80
Backhoe	78
AC paver/dike paver	77

Source: Federal Highway Administration (FHWA) 2006

Notes: dBA = decibel (A-weighted scale) L_{MAX} = maximum noise level

Construction Schedule

Construction is anticipated to begin in 2025. Construction on the bridge deck and bridge railings would last approximately 300 working days. Construction in the river would last approximately 60 days and be limited to June 1 thru October 31.

Conservation Measures

All project elements and construction will occur within the State ROW. Caltrans is proposing to implement a number of general conservation measures such as standard Best Management Practices (BMPs) and other measures. Please refer to the project BA for these BMPs. The following conservation measures are specific with regard to the CRR and LFS.

California Ridgway's Rail

1. No in-water work activity or work on the roadway surface within 700 feet of suitable CRR marsh habitat will occur from February 1 to August 31 during the CRR nesting season. Pile driving for the fender replacement at bridge bents 7 and 8 will be limited to occur outside of nesting season (February 1 through August 31) and only during daytime hours.
2. To minimize adverse effects of individual CRR, initial ground disturbance from upland activities within or adjacent to CRR suitable habitat will not occur within 2 hours before or after extreme high tides (6.5 feet or above, as measured at the Petaluma River Bridge). This is when the marsh plain is inundated and protective cover for CRR is limited.
3. A Service-approved biological monitor will be present onsite to monitor for CRR during the operation of large equipment within 300 feet of salt marsh areas.
4. The bridge rail work for all demolition and reconstruction takes place behind a temporary guardrail and will be restricted to daytime hours only.
5. During pile-driving events, Caltrans will monitor sound levels and cease work if 95 dB is measured at 150 feet from the source.

Longfin Smelt

1. In-channel work will be scheduled between June 1 and October 31 (September 1 to October 31 for pile driving).
2. During pile-driving events, Caltrans will monitor in-water sound pressure levels. Sound levels during pile installation will be used to establish effects at the monitoring locations in consultation with agencies.
3. All in-water pile driving in water depths greater than 2 feet at any time during work will use an underwater sound pressure attenuation system such as a bubble curtain system.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action,” (50 CFR 402.02). In this location, the Petaluma River defines the jurisdictional boundary between Marin and Sonoma counties. For the purposes of the effects assessment, the project is located on and underneath the SR 37 Petaluma River Bridge deck, within the aquatic environment of the Petaluma River, and within the tidal marsh habitats bordering the sides of Petaluma River. The Action Area equals approximately 156.4 acres in total and consists of the approximately 13.4 acres of the Petaluma Bridge Deck and associated ROW that extends east and west of the Petaluma Bridge, the approximately 114 acres of the aquatic environment within the Petaluma River that will experience underwater sound pressure effects from pile driving, and the approximately 29 acres of tidal marsh habitat

surrounding the project area that supports CRR and would be subject to pile driving noise effects.

ANALYTICAL FRAMEWORK for the JEOPARDY DETERMINATION

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the range wide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current range wide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action but that are not part of the action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the status of the species, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of the Species

California Ridgway’s Rail

Information about the California Ridgway’s rail biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the California Ridgway's rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Longfin Smelt

The Service listed the longfin smelt DPS as endangered on July 30, 2024 (Service 2024a). For the comprehensive assessment of the longfin smelt DPS, please refer to the proposed listing rule at <https://www.govinfo.gov/content/pkg/FR-2024-07-30/pdf/2024-16380.pdf#page=1> and the *Species Status Assessment for the San Francisco Bay-Delta Distinct Population Segment of the Longfin Smelt* at <https://ecos.fws.gov/ServCat/DownloadFile/253023> (Service 2024b). Critical habitat has not yet been proposed.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The proposed project is located over the Petaluma River and extends east and west of the Petaluma River. It is also located approximately 1 mile from the mouth of the Petaluma River where it meets the northern shore of the San Pablo Bay. The terrestrial portion of the proposed project consists of the Petaluma Bridge and the associated ROW of SR 37. Habitats nearby are a mix of agricultural lands with minimal urban development to the northeast and a mix of undisturbed ruderal lands interspersed with developed residential lots to the west/southwest. The aquatic portion of the proposed project consists primarily of deep riverine habitat with sand substrate that transitions laterally to tidal marsh habitats with emergent vegetation that occur along both sides of the Petaluma River.

California Ridgway's Rail

There are several acres of suitable breeding and foraging tidal marsh habitat on both sides of the Petaluma River that extend north and south of the bridge that support CRR. There are also numerous current detections of CRR in these tidal marsh habitats of the Lower Petaluma River (Green Point Marshes, Carl's Marsh, Sonoma Baylands Restoration, Petaluma River Mouth) within 1 mile of the Action Area with the nearest detection approximately 1,500 feet from where pile driving is proposed to occur (Point Blue Conservation Science 2023). Because of the proximity of known current occurrences of CRR and suitable habitat within and around the Action Area, presence of the species is presumed.

Longfin Smelt

The aquatic environment of the San Pablo Bay supports habitat for the species which extends throughout San Pablo Bay to the mouth of the Petaluma River. There are records of this species

within the northern portion of the San Pablo Bay and into the Petaluma River (Service 2024b) and longfin smelt are known to spawn in the Petaluma River. As water warms in the later spring and early summer, the young fish move seaward to cooler, higher salinity habitats in San Pablo and San Francisco Bays, and an unknown fraction of these juvenile fish enter the Pacific Ocean (Young *et al.* 2024). Thereafter, longfin smelt remain predominantly west of Carquinez Strait until some individuals return to lower salinity water in the fall.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it would not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. *Effects of the Action* may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

The primary element of the project that would likely cause adverse effects to the CRR and LFS is pile driving for the fender system of the bridge pier. The other elements of the proposed project occur on the bridge deck of the Petaluma Bridge, within the SR 37 ROW, and are outside of listed species habitats. Petaluma Bridge and the associated SR 37 ROW is the main thoroughfare for vehicle traffic around the northern shore of San Pablo Bay and experiences consistent heavy vehicle traffic. The other construction elements aside from pile driving are not anticipated to create noise or visual disturbances above normal ambient background levels and therefore, are not likely to adversely affect CRR and LFS.

California Ridgway's Rail

The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance that will exceed ambient conditions in tidal marsh habitats that support CRR year-round in and around the proposed project Action Area. Pile driving noise and vibration may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual CRR to flush from cover or prevent them from seeking available cover that could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Caltrans proposes to implement noise monitoring measures to ensure noise levels stay under 95 dB at 150 feet. The pile driving for the fender system of the bridge pier is approximately 85 feet from the edge of the western shore of the Petaluma River and 470 feet from the edge of the eastern shore of the Petaluma River where suitable tidal marsh habitats occur. Modeling by Caltrans indicates pile driving noise is approximately 83 dB when it reaches habitat for CRR and normal ambient background noise levels from vehicle traffic during the day is approximately 84-86 dB. Additionally, in an effort to minimize adverse effects to CRR, pile driving is proposed to occur from September 1 to October 31 to avoid the breeding season for CRR.

*Longfin Smelt*Pile Driving

The proposed project will likely generate temporary noise and visual disturbance that will exceed ambient conditions in areas that support LFS in the aquatic environment. Equipment noise, vibration, and visual disturbance may interfere with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, spawning, rearing, movement within the aquatic environment, and other essential behaviors.

Elevated noise levels can cause sub-lethal injuries affecting survival and fitness. Similarly, if injury does not occur, noise may modify fish behavior that may make them more susceptible to predation. Intolerable levels of disturbance that may force individual fish to flee from the area or prevent them from seeking available cover could expose them to a predation risk that otherwise would not occur. Fish suffering damage to hearing organs may suffer equilibrium problems and may have a reduced ability to detect predators and prey. Other types of sub-lethal injuries can place the fish at increased risk of predation and disease. Adverse effects on survival and fitness can occur even in the absence of overt injury. Exposure to elevated noise levels can cause a temporary shift in hearing sensitivity, decreasing sensory capability for periods lasting from hours to days (Turnpenny *et al.* 1994; Hastings *et al.* 1996).

The Service anticipates that juvenile or adult LFS may be injured or killed from construction activities due to the nature of the proposed project (pile driving), location, and duration of the proposed project. Caltrans proposes to minimize and possibly avoid these adverse effects by conducting in-water activities between June 1 and October 31 (September 1 to October 31 for pile driving) when LFS are least likely to be present.

Underwater sound pressure waves can harass and harm fish species (Reyff 2003; Abbott and Bing-Sawyer 2002; Caltrans 2001; Longmuir and Lively 2001; Stotz and Colby 2001). As the pressure wave passes through a fish, the swim bladder is rapidly squeezed due to the high pressure, and then rapidly expanded as the under-pressure component of the wave passes through the fish. This can cause adverse effects including rupture of the swim bladder, rupture of capillaries, internal hemorrhage, neurological stress, and auditory damage. Extreme sound waves can cause instantaneous death, latent death within minutes after exposure, or can occur several days later.

Among the construction activities likely to generate noise, the use of impact hammers for pile installation poses the greatest risk to fish because the levels of underwater noise produced by impulsive types of sounds can reach levels of sufficient intensity to injure or kill fish (Popper and Hastings 2009). Factors that may influence the potential for injury include species, life stage, and size of fish; type and size of pile and hammer; frequency and duration of pile driving; site characteristics (e.g., water depth); and distance of fish from the source. Dual interim criteria representing the acoustic thresholds associated with the onset of physiological effects in fish have been established to provide guidance for assessing the potential for injury resulting from pile-driving noise (Fisheries Hydroacoustic Working Group 2008) (Table 2). These criteria have

been established only for impact pile driving. Other pile-driving methods such as vibratory, oscillatory, and drilling methods generally produce more continuous, lower energy sounds below the thresholds associated with injury. No established noise thresholds currently are associated with continuous sound waves, and vibratory and oscillation methods generally are considered effective measures for avoiding or minimizing the risk of injury of fish from pile-driving noise.

Table 2. Interim Criteria for Assessing the Potential for Injury to Fish from Pile-Driving Activities

Interim Criteria	Agreement in Principle
Peak sound pressure level (SPL)	206 dB re 1 μ Pa (for all sizes of fish)
Cumulative sound exposure level (SEL)	187 dB re 1 μ Pa ² -sec—for fish size \geq 2 grams 183 dB re 1 μ Pa ² -sec—for fish size $<$ 2 grams
Behavioral (RMS)	150 dB re 1 μ Pa (for all sizes of fish)

Source: Fisheries Hydroacoustic Working Group 2008

dB re 1 μ Pa = dB referenced to a pressure of 1 microPascal

dB re 1 μ Pa²-sec = dB referenced to a pressure of 1 microPascal squared per second RMS = root mean square

The dual criteria are: (1) 206 dB for peak SPL and (2) 187 dB for cumulative SEL for fish larger than 2 grams and 183 dB SEL for fish smaller than 2 grams. The peak SPL threshold is considered the maximum SPL a fish can receive from a single strike without injury. The cumulative SEL threshold is considered the total amount of acoustic energy that a fish can receive from single or multiple strikes without injury. The cumulative SEL threshold is based on the total daily exposure of a fish to noise from sources that are discontinuous (in this case, noise that occurs up to 12 hours a day, with 12 hours between exposures). This assumes that fish are able to recover from any effects during this 12-hour period between exposures. These adverse effects will be partially minimized, but not eliminated, by the utilization of the proposed *Conservation Measures* such as implementing a pile-driving attenuation plan (bubble curtain system) that reduces these peak thresholds and underwater hydroacoustic effects. Additionally, in an effort to minimize adverse effects to LFS, pile driving is proposed to occur from September 1 to October 31 to avoid the spawning season for LFS.

If LFS are present in the Action Area during the proposed in-water work, there is the possibility of adverse physical lethal and sub-lethal effects associated with sound pressure waves from the installation of piles. It is unlikely that individuals would be affected by the 183 dB cumulative SEL over the course of a workday as they would likely disperse away from and avoid the hydroacoustic source. Mortality associated with the 206-dB peak sound level is not anticipated to be reached.

Turbidity and Contaminants

Construction activities would result in disturbances that are likely to temporarily increase turbidity and suspended sediment within the Action Area. Although LFS are adapted to living in turbid environments, localized increases could adversely affect individual LFS that may be present. Effects of increased turbidity and suspended sediment may temporarily degrade water quality, reduce prey resources, disturb habitat, and impede movements of LFS. Spills or other

chemical contamination from construction equipment could also negatively affect habitat and re-suspended sediments can sometimes elevate toxic levels in water. Implementation of the *Conservation Measures* would minimize but not eliminate the potential for these adverse effects to occur.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section; they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species*, the *Environmental Baseline*, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the State Route 37 Petaluma River Bridge Project, Marin County, California is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the CRR or the LFS. This is based on: (1) the relatively small impact the proposed project is anticipated to have on the CRR and LFS due to the implementation of seasonal work windows and short timeframe of pile driving (10-18 days); and (2) implementation of the *Conservation Measures* to minimize the adverse effects on individual CRR and LFS and their habitats that are present during the construction.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by Caltrans so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for

the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. Caltrans has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If Caltrans (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, Caltrans must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(4)].

Amount or Extent of Take

California Ridgway's Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of CRR will be difficult to detect or quantify because of their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy in tidal marsh habitats resulting in low detectability. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), a surrogate for individual animals may be used to express the amount or extent of anticipated incidental take in the Incidental Take Statement (ITS). Surrogates are used for this ITS because it is difficult to accurately quantify and monitor the amount or number of individuals that are expected to be incidentally taken as a result of the proposed action. Therefore, the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual CRR. The Service anticipates incidental take of all CRR within the approximate 29 acres of tidal marsh habitat in the form of harm from the impairment of essential behaviors through the noise effects of pile driving. The Service anticipates that the number of CRR adversely affected will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the following Reasonable and Prudent Measure, take in the form of harm from impairing essential behaviors within the 29-acre portion of the Action Area will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act. The Service does not anticipate that take in the form of wounding or killing of CRR during construction will occur due to the nature of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service is not exempting take in the form of wound or kill for any CRR during construction activities from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Longfin Smelt

The Service anticipates that juvenile and adult LFS will be subject to take in the form of harm and mortality from exposure to predation that would otherwise not occur from LFS actively attempting to avoid the area of disturbance, and anticipates injury or mortality of LFS if they are within the SPL and SEL distances of the Action Area during impact pile-driving. In accordance with 50 CFR 402.14(i)(1)(i), a surrogate for individual animals may be used to express the amount or extent of anticipated incidental take in the ITS. Surrogates are used for this ITS because it is difficult to accurately quantify and monitor the amount or number of individuals that are expected to be incidentally taken as a result of the proposed action. Therefore, the Service is using habitat affected as a surrogate for individual LFS. The Service anticipates take in the form of harm, injury, and mortality of all LFS within approximately 114 acres of the aquatic environment within the Action Area. The Service anticipates that the number of LFS adversely

affected will be low or minimal, but not completely reduced, based on the conditions of the project and implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures*. Upon implementation of the Reasonable and Prudent Measures, incidental take associated with the project will become exempt from the prohibitions described under section 9 of the Act.

Effect of the Take

The Service determines that the level of take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the CRR or the LFS.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

The following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the effects of the proposed project to the CRR and LFS:

1. Caltrans shall minimize effects to CRR and LFS to the fullest extent possible.

Term and Condition

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, Caltrans shall ensure that its contractors comply with the following term and condition, which implement its respective reasonable and prudent measure described above. This term and condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. Caltrans shall implement the *Conservation Measures* as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* and comply with this biological opinion.
 - b. Caltrans shall educate and inform personnel involved in the project as to the *Conservation Measures* and *Term and Condition* in this biological opinion.
 - c. Caltrans shall ensure its contractors comply with the *Reporting Requirements* below.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the project is approached or exceeded, Caltrans shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, Caltrans must reinstate formal consultation as per 50 CFR 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed project. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, Caltrans shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken* section below.

2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and CNDDDB (<https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/BIOS>).

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals Taken

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation for the State Route 37 Petaluma River Bridge Project, Marin County, California as provided in 50 CFR §402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response to Brian Hansen, Senior Fish and Wildlife Biologist, at Brian_Hansen@fws.gov or (916) 930-5642 or Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager, at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to Service file number 2022-0044363-S7-001-R001 in any future correspondence regarding this project.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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